

Synthesis of some New Derivatives of 6-Chloro-4-(hydrazido)-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one

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Sequential treatment of 6-chloro-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (1) with ethyl chloroformate and hydrazine hydrate gives the title compound (3) that has been converted to oxadiazole (5) and imidazole (6), via the benzoyl derivative (4).

Oxazine derivatives are used in medicine due to their significant bacteriocidal¹, fungicidal², anthelmintic³, antitubercular⁴ and anticancer⁵ properties. Various workers have reported the synthesis of 1,2- and 1,3-benzoxazines^{6,7}. Very little work has been done on the synthesis of 1,4-oxazines. Recently, Shridhar *et al.*⁸ have synthesised some 1,4-benzoxazine derivatives and screened them for their antiinflammatory property.

- 1 R=H
2 R=COOEt
3 R=CONHNH₂
4 R=CONHNHCOPh

- 5 X=O
6 X=NH

The starting compound 6-chloro-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (1) was prepared by the base catalysed cyclisation of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetamide. Treatment of (1) with ethyl chloroformate in the presence of triethyl amine gave the corresponding *N*-acyl derivative (2) which was converted to the title hydrazide (3) by refluxing in ethanol containing hydrazine. Stirring 3 with benzoyl chloride in pyridine gave 4 as a viscous mass which without further purification was subjected to acid catalysed cyclisation⁹ to produce the oxadiazole (5), and heated with ammonia¹⁰ to afford the imidazole (6).

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra on a Varian A-90 (EM-390) instrument using TMS as internal reference. Melting points were determined using a Thomas Hoover capillary melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of the products was checked by tlc.

The methods followed for the synthesis of the compounds are described below.

6-Chloro-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (1): A mixture of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetamide (9.0 g, 0.041 mol) and triethylamine (3.0 g, 0.03 mol) in dry methanol (30 ml) was refluxed on oil-bath for 6 h at 110°, and then the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with ether and concentrated. The deposited solid was recrystallised from ethanol to yield 1 (6.0 g, 80%), m.p. 138° (Found: C, 52.25; H, 3.22; N, 7.56. C₈H₈NO₂Cl requires C, 52.31; H, 3.26; N, 7.63%); ν_{\max} (nujol): 1695 (C=O) and 3200 cm⁻¹ (NH); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 256.2 nm; δ (CD₂Cl₂) 4.60 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, C₈H), 7.4 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 3.0 Hz, C₇-H), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 3.0 Hz, C₆-H) and 8.8 (1H, br s, NH).

6-Chloro-4-carbethoxy-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (2): A mixture of 1 (4.5 g, 0.024 mol) and ethylchloroformate (8.0 g, 0.073 mol) in methanol (10 ml) was refluxed at 90° for 10 h, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residual liquid on distillation gave 2 (3.0 g, 60%), b.p. 294° (Found: C, 56.65; H, 3.85; N, 5.45. C₁₁H₁₀NO₄Cl requires C, 51.66; H, 3.91; N, 5.48%); ν_{\max} (liquid) 1735 cm⁻¹ (broad, C=O and ester C=O); δ (CCl₄) 1.3 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 4.6 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.8 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, C₈-H), 7.2 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0, 2.5 Hz, C₇-H) and 7.35 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, C₆-H).

6-Chloro-4-(hydrazido)-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H) one (3): A mixture of 2 (2.5 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (2.0 g, 0.04 mol) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was heated at 70-80° for 15 min. The separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol to yield 3 (1.8 g, 76%), m.p. 153° (Found: C, 44.65; H, 3.30; N, 17.37. C₈H₈N₂O₂Cl requires C, 44.72; H, 3.31; N, 17.40%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3200-3300 (doublet NHNH₂) and 1695 cm⁻¹ (δ -lactam ketone); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 285 nm; δ (CDCl₂) 2.1 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.52 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, C₈-H), 7.2 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5, 2.5 Hz, C₇-H) and 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, C₆-H).

6-Chloro-4-(5'-phenyl-1',3',4'-oxadiazol-2'-yl)-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazine-3(2H)-one (5): A mixture of 3 (0.5 g, 0.002 mol) and benzoyl chloride (0.5 g, 0.003 mol) in pyridine (2 ml) was swirled for

10 min. The white solid that separated out on cooling was extracted in ether and the extract concentrated to give a viscous mass which on further treatment with concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.2 ml) gave a solid. Its extraction in xylene and removal of solvent from the extract under reduced pressure yielded **5** (0.49 g, 59%), m.p. 160° (xylene) (Found : C, 58.55; H, 3.00; N, 12.80. $C_{16}H_{10}N_3O_3Cl$ requires C, 58.63; H, 3.05; N, 12.82%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1695 (N=C) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CCl_4) 4.9 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.3 (5H, m, Ar-H) and 7.8 (3H, m, Ar-H).

6-Chloro-4'-(5'-phenyl-1',3',4'-imidiazol-2'-yl)-3,4-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H, one) (6): A mixture of **3** (0.5 g, 0.002 mol) and benzoyl chloride (0.5 g, 0.003 mol) in pyridine (2 ml) was stirred for 10 min. The separated solid was extracted with ether and concentrated to give a viscous mass. The viscous mass on heating with NH_3 for ~ 5 h afforded a solid mass which was extracted in xylene and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue

obtained was recrystallised from xylene to yield **6** (0.45 g, 67%), m.p. 151° (Found : C, 58.73; H, 3.30; N, 17.12. $C_{16}H_{11}N_4O_2Cl$ requires C, 58.80; H, 3.37; N, 17.15%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3200 (NH), 1696 (N=C) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CCl_4) 4.85 (2H, s, OCH_2), 7.2 and 7.6 (8H, m, Ar-H).

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